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One Health Surveillance Initiatives in Europe

An inventory of implemented, integrated, cross-sector initiatives in different member states

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One Health Surveillance Initiatives in Europe

An inventory of implemented, integrated, cross-sector initiatives in different member states

One Health Surveillance Initiatives in Europe

An inventory and description of the variety of implemented, integrated, cross-sector initiatives in different member states

One Health is defined as cross-sector collaboration to design and implement programmes, policies, legislation and research to achieve better public and animal health outcomes. This is particularly relevant in the control of zoonoses and combatting antibiotic resistance (WHO 2019; OIE 2019). One Health traditionally includes public health, animal health and the environment. However, ORION and other projects defines that collecting and interpreting data from all three sectors is not a requirement to characterize a system as One Health, as long as systematic and organized collaborations between any of the sectors can increase efficiency, cost-effectiveness and cost-benefits of currently running systems (Bordier et al., 2018,).

In surveillance of foodborne pathogens and antimicrobial resistance (AMR), cross-sector collaboration according to the One Health principle is likely to have a positive effect on the sensitivity, timeliness and on the efficiency of control. Traditionally, the EU Member States (MS) carried out surveillance in individual sectors according to target populations with well-defined areas of responsibilities, communication channels and risk management roles. However, the advantages of using One Health (OH) principles is becoming more apparent. MS are beginning to define, structure and implement cross-sector collaboration more strategically, especially in the areas of foodborne zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance surveillance. It is rare to see full cross-sectorial surveillance systems, but smaller or more confined One Health surveillance initiatives (OHSI) exist in MS today. An initiative can be defined as a subsystem or component conceived to induce change in the larger system that it is a part of (Ruegg et al, 2018).

Usually, OHSI arise as a response to a specific need in the individual MS and continue to develop in that context for a specific purpose. The description of OHSI are often not published and often only apparent to actual stakeholders, the initiative participants and users within the MS. Some initiatives are supported by legislation, some arise due to resource-saving activities and others are just a formalisation of groups of people, who need to talk regularly to understand the surveillance outputs. Knowing more about what works for some MS, may inspire others to consider enhancing their OH surveillance.

Figure 1 shows a schematic illustration of sector-specific surveillance pathways suggesting what an OHSI could be. The red pathway illustrates the surveillance pathway in the animal and/or food sector, while the blue illustrates the public health surveillance pathway. Mostly, the two pathways run in parallel with surveillance components for the same pathogens, but some initiatives or even full components connect the two sectors (orange) and constitute an OHSI. Usually, an OHSI will address only a few steps in the surveillance pathway and apply to just one or two components of the full surveillance systems.

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of potential One Health Surveillance Initiatives between sectorial surveillance pathways for a surveillance component.

An OHSI can connect one or more steps in the otherwise sector-specific pathways. It could be a cross-sector sample collection approach, a multi-sector expert group, multi-sector outbreak detection team or an institute dealing with emerging hazards in multiple populations. Some OHSI may be so comprehensive and established that they can become surveillance components in their own right. Smaller initiatives are more common and can be fluent and intangible, interconnecting or overarching several steps in the pathway.

Our objective was 1) to identify, collate and describe current European OHSI, to inspire other countries to enhance their one health surveillance; and 2) to identify gaps in the surveillance chains, which may benefit from OHSI in the future.

Materials and methods

Data collection

Data was collected using a two-step approach with a screening questionnaire and then approaching a subset of responders for semi-structured interviews.

Survey questionnaire

An initial screening questionnaire to identify existing OHS initiatives in surveillance of foodborne diseases in European Union (EU) countries was distributed by email to Focal Points for the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and through the Food- and Waterborne Disease and Zoonoses Network of the European

Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (FWD-Net, ECDC) (Appendix 1). The aim was to reach agencies and administrations carrying out public health, food and animal surveillance. As part of the ORION project survey, all ORION partners also received the screening questionnaire. Furthermore, members of known OHSIs in Kenya, Singapore, Brazil and the United Kingdom were approached for participation.

On receipt, all replies were categorized according to country, sectors involved and steps in the surveillance pathway.

Selection of initiatives for interview

A subset of eligible OHSI were selected for semi-structured interviews. The subset was designed to reflect a similar distribution of steps in the surveillance pathway as the screening questionnaires. Furthermore, it aimed to ensure that all steps were represented, include as many countries as possible and avoid repetition of very similar initiatives. For the OHSI to be considered for an interview, the OHSI needed to:

- Focus on surveillance foodborne pathogens as defined in the ORION Glossary definition (WHO definition; FAO term portal; OIE glossary).
- Be a surveillance activity as defined by the WHO and RiskSur (WHO definition; RiskSur, 2018), excluding initiatives focused purely on response or operations.
- Include collaboration between at least two sectors of public health, animal health, environment and food.

Semi-structured interview

Selected initiatives were contacted by email and asked for an interview to obtain further details. A semi-structured interview was carried out by phone and captured a general description of the initiative, as well as a characterization of the OH integration involved. Furthermore, it allowed interviewees to add their own points of view and comments. The semi-structured interview was designed based on previous experience and the interview check-list is available in Appendix 2 (Berg, 2007; Ellis-Iversen et al, 2010). All interviews were recorded after agreement from the interviewees and the sound files were later transcribed. A one-page summary of each OHSI was prepared and sent to the interviewees for review and approval to ensure that the OHSI was presented correctly. Descriptive analysis was carried out on the types of initiatives, using both ORION classifications according to steps in the surveillance pathway and descriptions parameters defined by Bordier et al. (2018).

Results & Discussion

Study population

The initial screening questionnaire was answered by 20 countries, identifying a total of 78 OHSI. A total of 71% was received through the EFSA focal points network, 13% through the ORION platform, 9% through the FWD-Net and six (8%) OHSI originated from the people directly contacted.

From the initially received OHSIs, 38 (49%) fit all criteria for interview selection. The reasons for lack of fitness were commonly that the submitted initiatives were not surveillance, but research or outbreak

control initiatives; the initiatives were in the planning phase; did not include foodborne zoonoses; or did not have sufficient collaboration/integration to be classified as OH.

To avoid describing several similar initiatives, 22 invitations for interviews were extended, resulting in 16 interviews from 10 EU countries and Singapore. Two interviews were excluded from publication: One, because the initiative could not be classified as surveillance and a second because the interviewee did not respond to the request for approval of the description.

The briefness of the screening questionnaire was deliberate to ensure a high number of respondents rather than to capture detail, resulting in too sparse and uncertain data for further analyses. However, it also excluded further analysis on the screening data.

One Health Surveillance Initiatives

A total of 15 initiatives were included in the further work. The OHSI are briefly described in table 1 and for a more detailed description, see appendix 3. "Inspiration and ideas- One Health Integration in Surveillance" (Ellis-Iversen et al, 2019).

The majority of the OHSI represented four types of initiatives: 1) cross-sector laboratory analyses, 2) groups to discuss and understand surveillance outcomes, 3) surveillance outcome communications to the wider community and 4) governance structures across sectors.

The cross-sector laboratory initiatives were implemented either for rare diseases or for novel or advanced analysis, where all strains of one species may be sent for typing or sequencing in one sectoral laboratory that has specialized in the methodologies. Apart from saving resources, this may also lead to faster response and more collaboration between sectors.

Groups of experts from several sectors to discuss and interpret surveillance result were also reported from several countries. In two countries, these were established groups to deal with new, emerging or changing pathogens to generate prioritized advice on response and control and often included decision-makers as well as scientific experts. Other countries reported cross-sector groups that meet regularly and discuss the current situation and outbreaks and interpret or explain changes together.

Publishing a joint report on zoonoses from several sectors was common in the screening questionnaires, probably because it is a logic next step after the joint reporting by ECDC and EFSA. Some variation was observed between countries on how much the sectors shared data, collaborated on result interpretation and collation of the report.

A cross-sector governance structure for zoonotic or AMR surveillance was reported from several countries. The governance structures were all at national level and were responsible for varying levels of strategy, optimization, communication and prioritization of response.

Table 1. Examples of OHSI from EU MS and Singapore

Name of initiative	Country	Surveillance sectors covered	Steps in the surveillance pathway covered	What is shared
Surveillance of Human Listeriosis	France	Human Food Some industry	Laboratory analysis Data transfer and collation Data analysis and interpretation	Bacterial isolates, genetic/typing information and some metadata
Food Bug	Finland	Human Food Animal	Data transfer and collation Data analysis and interpretation	Molecular typing results and metadata
The Business Intelligence System (BI)	Switzerland	Some food Animal Human intended	Data transfer and collation	IT-infrastructure for data storage, Data warehouse IT-technical
The Zoonoses Assembly	Denmark	Human Food Animal	Data interpretation Outcome communication	Surveillance outputs, aggregated data for joint discussion and interpretation, food borne outbreak information
Working Group One Health (WGOH)	Switzerland	Human Food Animal	Outcome communication (Aim to expand along the pathway)	Surveillance results and some interpretation for advice to SBOH
Annual report of Zoonoses	Estonia	Human Food Animal	Data transfer and collation Outcome communication	Vet and food data collation including metadata, aggregated data from PH and livestock and food industry Report published jointly
Report on Surveillance of Infectious Disease in Animal and Humans	Sweden	Human Food Animal Industry	Data analysis and interpretation Outcome communication	Aggregated data from SVA, industry and human. Some degree of collaboration around data interpretation. Joint publication.
Zoonoses Working Group in the Croatian Food Agency	Croatia	Human Food Animal	Design, adjustment and optimization Outcome communication	Joint report, surveillance optimization discussions, surveillance outcome sharing.
Brucellosis surveillance	France	Human Food Animal	Data analysis and interpretation	Sharing of strains and typing information.
Veterinary Risk Group	UK	Food Animal Some human Indirect industry	Response and prioritization	Surveillance outcomes, joint risk assessment and advice for response.
Early Warning Meeting on Zoonoses	The Netherlands	Human Food Animal	Response and prioritization	Surveillance outcomes and joint risk assessment and response
Subsidiary Body One Health (SBOH)	Switzerland	Human Food Animal Environment	Design, adjustment and optimization Response and prioritization Intention: Expansion to decisions/ advice in the full surveillance pathway.	Development of The National Strategy on Antibiotic Resistance StAR Response advice
The Swedish Zoonoses Council	Sweden	Human Food Animal Feed	Optimization Response and prioritization	Surveillance outputs, control strategies and surveillance priorities, joint advice on priorities
DANMAP Surveillance	Denmark	Human Food Animal Indirect industry	Some design and optimization Data analysis & interpretation Outcome communication	Sharing of data, some joint data interpretation, joint reporting, communications, advice and planning
The Antimicrobial Resistance Coordinating Office (AMRCO) -established 2019	Singapore	Human Food Animal Relevant industries	Design, adjustment and optimization Data analysis and interpretation (future) Outcome communication (future)	Collating data from all sectors on AMR and where available AMU. Plans to share work along the whole surveillance chain apart from direct laboratory work or primary data collection.

Nearly all the 15 OHSI addressed several steps in the surveillance pathway. The distribution is presented in figure 2.

Figure 2. Number of One Health Surveillance Initiatives (OHSI) addressing each of the steps in the surveillance pathway.

Almost the whole surveillance pathway was addressed by OHSI somewhere in the EU. The exception was ‘sample collection’, which no OHSI addressed. Since the samples are collected in different populations, this would probably not be an effective step to implement cross-sectorial work, as the subjects would probably not be willing to submit samples to professionals of another sector e.g. patients to a veterinarian.

Only one OHSI included the laboratory analysis on samples from several sectors. Traditionally, each sector has their own laboratories and since this structure is very physical, well established and functional, it may take time to change or not be a cost-effective place to integrate sectors. Nonetheless, adoption of next-generation sequencing methods may lead the way for more cross-sector integration. The high investment in equipment and training of personnel as well as non-standardised interpretation methods may lead to countries deciding to invest in one specialized national laboratory rather than several.

Once electronic surveillance data has been produced, the number of submitted OHSI increased, suggesting it is easier to share data than samples and physical infrastructure. Despite quite a lot of data sharing was reported, it was often in aggregated and interpreted form and no full-functioning cross-sector raw capture were reported. One initiative had developed the database and platform system for data integration, but was still struggling with the legislation around data sharing and the motivation of other sectors to join. It is clearly a complicated step in OH surveillance and the discussions are currently ongoing in many countries.

Data analysis and interpretation were addressed by many cross-sectorial initiatives. However, it usually only included reporting trends, spotting outbreaks or new threats in fora, where each sector brought their own analyses results for cross-sector discussion or publication. For epidemiological analysis of surveillance data, sector-specific expertise and knowledge are needed and unless, the expertise is integrated, the value of cross-sector data analysis is limited. Furthermore, truly integrated data analysis may also be hindered by data protection laws. However, it may be possible to integrate this step further than the examples gathered in this survey, by enhancing the collaboration of the experts.

OHSI was also in place to generate prioritised advice on response and resource allocation based on structured processes and multi-sectorial risk assessments. These were developed in MS, where serious outbreaks had highlighted a need for cross-sector prioritisation. It is possible that more MS may develop similar OHSI in the future, if a need is identified.

Quite a few OHSI presented governance structures often supported by legislation and implemented to aid decision-making and timeliness of response to surveillance. The success of these governance structures varied, depending on the remit and the support they received in the country. The AMRCO in Singapore was newly constituted commencing with a governance structure, but with the aim to develop a One Health Surveillance System with most of the steps in the pathway flowing through this body.

One Health Surveillance Initiatives are implemented in EU MS more frequently in some countries than others. The OHSI were usually established as a response to a need or a situation in the specific MS and reflect many different ways of doing OH surveillance. It is unlikely that all OHSI will apply to all MS. However, they are likely to inspire and may with adjustment improve surveillance in another MS.

Since all EU MS have established surveillance systems and infrastructures for zoonotic pathogens, all new initiatives need to fit into the structures and traditions of the existing systems. This may, in some cases, lead to very good and strong initiatives, but in others, the established system, staff and traditions may slow or even hinder implementation of cross-sector working.

Interestingly, the call for actions on antimicrobial resistance by WHO, FAO and OIE has initiated OH surveillance in countries, where no previous systems exists and it is possible that strategies and initiatives from these countries will inspire EU MS in the future. The ARMCO in Singapore was included in this project to reflect this. The coordination office will set up a surveillance system for antimicrobial use and resistance across veterinary, food and human populations with very few previously established systems or infrastructure to consider.

Furthermore, in MS with already functioning surveillance systems, it is uncertain whether cross-sector working in all steps in the surveillance pathway will improve surveillance value or cost-effectiveness. The subjects being surveyed i.e. humans, farms, food companies or others need to trust the system, the data flow channels and the people handling their data, otherwise they will be less likely to participate and the surveillance value will reduce compared to the existing systems.

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List of appendices

1. Screening questionnaire for One Health initiatives on foodborne disease and AMR surveillance in the European Union
2. Interview outline
3. One Health Integration in Surveillance – inspiration and ideas. Available on: <http://www.food.dtu.dk/-/media/Institutter/Foedevareinstituttet/Publikationer/Pub-2019/Rapport-One-Health-Integration-in-Surveillance.ashx?la=da>

Appendix 1

Screening questionnaire for One Health initiatives on foodborne disease and AMR surveillance in the European Union

We are looking for One Health surveillance initiatives in European Union countries, in order to generate an idea catalogue for knowledge sharing and inspiration for other countries. We would greatly appreciate your participation.

The main idea of One Health Surveillance is to improve health and well-being through collaboration between public, food and veterinary sectors. ORION is a European Joint Project aiming to enhance One Health Surveillance, by increasing knowledge flow and data sharing. One of the project objectives is to generate an “idea catalogue” of established surveillance initiatives bridging animal, food and human sectors. The catalogue will be used to inspire other countries to enhance their own One Health Surveillance.

Please fill in one table for each One Health Surveillance initiative you have in your country. If you have several initiatives, copy and paste to generate as many tables as you need.

If you need inspiration or further clarification, please look at the examples below the tables.

Name or identifier of the initiative (if it has one)	
A brief description of the overall mandate or objectives of the initiative	
Which surveillance sectors (food, animal or human) does it encompass?	
A contact person for the initiative	
Website link - if applicable	
Published outputs – if applicable	

Name or identifier of the initiative (if it has one)	
A brief description of the overall mandate or objectives of the initiative	
Which surveillance sectors (food, animal or human) does it encompass?	
A contact person for the initiative	
Website link - if applicable	
Published outputs – if applicable	

EXAMPLES of One Health Surveillance Initiatives for inspiration:

- a) **A unified laboratory** performing typing or sequencing of human, food and/or animal isolates;
- b) **Multi-sector regular meetings** of people that discuss impact of surveillance outputs across sectors, e.g. public health impact of a new pathogen in animals. Examples: HAIRS & NARMS (<https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/human-animal-infections-and-risk-surveillance-group-hairs>) & (<https://www.cdc.gov/narms/index.html>)
- c) **Cross-sector collation and interpretation of surveillance outputs**, e.g. a national/regional report presenting quarterly/annual outputs from two or more sectors. Example: The Annual Report on Zoonoses in Denmark (<https://www.food.dtu.dk/Publikationer/Sygdomsfremkaldende-mikroorganismer/Zoonoser-aarlige-rapporter>)
- d) **Cross-sector analysis of data** to identify the most likely sources for the infections, outbreak detection etc;
- e) **One database storing genetic sequences or typing data** of isolates from human, food and/or animal samples, allowing for immediate comparisons. Example: PulseNet (<https://www.cdc.gov/pulsenet/index.html>);
- f) **One database** to store **information on surveillance data** from humans, food and/or animals, e.g. antimicrobial resistance, syndromic surveillance or prevalence data from surveillance programmes;
- g) **Shared multi-sector agencies/institutes/contracts to carry out surveillance**. Example: Sciensano (<https://www.sciensano.be/en>) in Belgium, formed by the merging of the Scientific Institute for Public Health and the National Institute for Animal Health;
- h) **Any other form of surveillance collaboration across public, food and veterinary health.....**

Please return the document to XXXXX, to whom you should also direct your queries for further information or questions.

Thank you for your collaboration. Your answers will help improve health and well-being in the EU.

If you would like to know more about ORION, please visit our webpage:

<https://onehealthjep.eu/structure/jip1-orion/>.

Appendix 2:

Interview outline

Name of initiative: _____

Interviewee: _____

Phone number: _____

OPENING (FOR INTERVIEWER USE):

Good (afternoon/day), thank you very much for taking my call and helping us with this interview. My name is xxx. I am a veterinary epidemiologist at the National Food Institute in Denmark, and my group focuses on providing scientific support for policy-making to national and international food authorities.

Right now, we have collected some really great One Health initiatives, and we would like to put them in an idea catalogue, for all countries to use for inspirations. To do that, I need more details about your initiative, so we have the same type of information for all the entries.

This interview is what we call a semi-structured interview, which means that there is some specific information I need, but what I am mostly interested in is what you have to tell me about the initiative. So I am talking a lot now, but from now on, I promise it will be mostly you. So, we are going to talk about <INITIATIVE NAME>.

IF RECORDING THE CALL, REMEMBER TO INFORM AND ASK FOR PERMISSION.

- 1 - Which pathogens or hazards is this initiative focused on?
- 2 - Geographical area coverage (national, supra-national, subnational). Country or area covered.
- 3 - *(Year of establishment)* On which year did the first collaborative efforts start?
- 4 - *(Type of initiative)* Would you describe it as an expert group, an institute, a programme, or something else?

Prompts:

- *Surveillance database, unified laboratory, laboratory database, joint reporting*
- *Main activities*

- 5 - What do you think was the reason/motivation for it to start, in the first place?

Prompts:

- *Outbreaks or need to reduce prevalence*
- *Visible need to improve sharing and communication between sectors*
- *Build on previous system (improvement)*
- *The problem is cross-sectoral, so the solution should also be*
- *New policy, or financing opportunity*

- 6 - Is it connected to other initiatives, as part of something bigger? A program, for example? Or is it a standalone effort?

- 7 - What is the rationale behind the initiative? The general objective, textbook version.

Prompts:

- *Surveillance objective: early detection (including outbreak detection) / monitoring of trends or occurrence, demonstrating freedom of disease*
- *Increasing communication between sectors*

8 - Which populations are covered in this program (if applicable)?

Prompts:

- *What animal species, or more than one*
- *What food products*
- *Any specific gender, age or occupational group in the human population?*
- *Who benefits from the final product?*

10 - Who is involved (which sectors, specific companies or institutions)?

Prompts:

- *Which institutions are involved (by name)*
- *Type of institutions (academia, governmental authority, inter-governmental agencies, industry)*
- *Are all stakeholders public?*
- *Does it involve the industry, or other private institutions?*
- *In which role?*

11 - Where does the funding come from?

12 - Who is collaborating, and where are the collaboration crossovers?

(FOR INTERVIEWER USE): Which levels of the One Health collaboration dimensions (Bourdier et al 2018) below occur in this initiative? Does it involve any other dimensions that you believe are missing from the list?

- *collaboration between institutions belonging to different sectors (animal health, public health, environmental health, etc.) for the coordination and the implementation of the surveillance system*
- *collaboration at the different scales of the decision-making process (administrative jurisdictional levels, community, etc.)*
- *collaboration across actors working in different disciplines (veterinary or human medicine, epidemiologist, biologist, entomologist, ecologist, economist, sociologist, etc.)*
- *collaboration through public-private partnerships.*

13 - How does the initiative use data? Is it lab results, or lab + metadata, for example? What is the data flow?

14 - What is the degree of collaboration?

(TABLE BELOW FOR INTERVIEWER USE): INTRODUCE IDEA, AND TRY TO FIGURE OUT FROM THE OPEN ANSWERS.

Prompts:

- *If they say "data", ask if it's samples, numbers in a computer, or what.*
- *When they say data collection, is that sample collection? Isolates? Information from a database? Hospital records?*

15 - Frequency of meetings, if applicable

16 - Are there any evidence of benefits coming from the collaboration?

Prompts:

- *Measurable outcomes*
- *Outputs*
- *Published outputs*
- *Are there any improvements that you can name, when comparing before and after the initiative was started?*
- *Did the initiative work?*
- *Does it meet its objectives?*
- *Which problems did it solve?*

17 - Main challenges

Prompts:

- *In case the interviewee believes the initiative didn't work, what were the main hurdles?*
- *Constraints in communication between human, animal and food*
- *Barriers for collaboration between human, animal and food*
- *Moving slower, after bold start*

18 - Is there anything else you believe is important that people know about <INITIATIVE NAME> and which you didn't have the chance to talk about during this interview?

Design, adjustment and optimization	Done separately in each sector	Done by a single sector for all components	Cross-sectoral consultation but done separately	
Data/sample collection	Done separately in each sector	Done by a single sector for all components	Harmonisation across sectors	Done by a multi-sectoral organization
Laboratory analysis	Done separately in each sector lab	Done by a single sector for all samples	Harmonisation across sector laboratories	Done by a multi-sectoral organization
Data transfer and collation	No data exchange	Notification of unusual events only	Continuous data exchange	
Data analysis and interpretation	Done separately in each sector	Done separately and then compared by a single sector	Jointly done by a single sector for all components	Jointly done by a multi-sectoral organisation
Outcome communication	Done separately in each sector	Joint dissemination in separate sectoral activities	Joint dissemination by a single sector	Jointly done by a multi-sectoral organisation
Response and prioritization	Done separately by each sector	Done by a single sector for all risks	Cross-sectoral consultation but done separately	Jointly done by a multi-sectoral organisation

CLOSING (FOR INTERVIEWER USE): Thank you very much for your collaboration and availability. Would you like to see my resulting draft and offer suggestions or corrections? We hope to have a final product out early next year. Also, would you like or allow it to contain the contact details for the responsible for the initiative?